

EVALUATING THE CODE GENERATION CAPABILITIES OF CHATGPT THROUGH C++ DATABASE MANAGEMENT TASKS

MOHAMMED ALABDULLATIF¹

Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, College of Computer Sciences and Information Technology, King Faisal University, Alahsa, Saudi Arabia.

E-mail: ¹maabdullatif@kfu.edu.sa

ABSTRACT

Large language models (LLMs) are becoming important tools in software engineering. These models, trained on large amounts of text, can understand and generate natural language with high accuracy. Today, they are being used across many stages of software development, from improving code quality and generating documentation to supporting natural language interaction with development tools. Among their many applications, code generation is one of the areas where these models have shown the greatest impact. This study explores the coding capabilities of ChatGPT GPT 4, a large language model introduced by OpenAI in May 2024. The model was evaluated on twenty C++ database management tasks, and the quality of its outputs was assessed using Cppcheck, a static code analysis tool. The results show that ChatGPT consistently produces executable C++ programs, though differences in code length and structure highlight its inherent nondeterministic nature. Most of the issues detected by static analysis were stylistic rather than functional or logical. Overall, this work provides empirical evidence on both the reliability and the current limitations of LLM based code generation, offering directions for future research.

Keywords: *Software Engineering, ChatGPT, Large Language Models, Coding, Programming Languages*

1. INTRODUCTION

Large Language Models (LLMs) are playing an increasingly central role in software engineering, especially in areas such as code generation, debugging, and documentation [1]. Tools like OpenAI's Codex [2] and GitHub Copilot [3], trained on vast and diverse codebases, can suggest code snippets, complete functions, or even generate entire programs from natural language prompts. Beyond generating code, they can improve documentation by producing clearer explanations of comments and function descriptions, helping bridge communication between technical and non-technical audiences.

LLMs boost developer productivity by offering context-aware suggestions and automating repetitive tasks [4]. Their strong performance in generating and completing code [5], [6], combined with their ability to identify common patterns in large datasets, has made them a valuable component of modern software development. These capabilities support faster workflows, assist with error detection, and contribute to more efficient development practices.

In this research, we evaluate the performance of ChatGPT GPT-4 on a collection of C++ database management tasks that share the same functional requirements but differ in context. The evaluation considers generation time, code length, executability, and static analysis using Cppcheck [7]. The goal is to examine both the strengths and limitations of ChatGPT in generating database-oriented C++ programs and to understand how it handles repeated generations of comparable tasks.

The contributions of this work are as follows:

1. We examine ChatGPT's performance across multiple repeated generations of comparable C++ database-management tasks, providing insight into the model's variability in structure and size of generated programs.
2. We evaluate the generated code using indicators such as generation time and code length. We also apply Cppcheck to examine code issues, and compute error density.
3. We identify practical limitations observed in repeated generations such as non-deterministic

structure, variable code size, and outline considerations for future research in AI-assisted code generation.

The objective of this study is to evaluate ChatGPT's ability to generate C++ code for database management tasks in a systematic and measurable way. Specifically, the study aims to: (1) assess the syntactic correctness of the generated programs across twenty structurally similar tasks; (2) analyse variation in program structure, length, and category across one hundred repeated generations per task; and (3) examine the static quality of the generated code using Cppcheck, including the detection of issues and the computation of task-level error density.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces background concepts essential for understanding this study. Section 3 presents the related work. Section 4 describes the methodology employed, and Section 5 reports the performance evaluation results. Section 7 compares our findings with existing works, and Section 7 provides the conclusion.

2. BACKGROUND

This section outlines the three main areas of this research: generative AI, large language models (LLMs), and ChatGPT and their relevance to software engineering, particularly code generation.

2.1 Generative AI

Generative AI focuses on creating new content, unlike traditional AI that mainly classifies or predicts. It can generate text, images, music, and even software code by learning patterns from training data [8], [9]. Foundational models include GANs, which improve outputs through adversarial training [10], and VAEs, which learn latent representations for data generation [11]. These methods are now applied in healthcare for drug design and protein prediction, in manufacturing for design optimization, and in software engineering for automatic code generation, bug fixing, and testing. [12], [13], [14].

2.2 Large Language Models (LLMs)

LLMs, such as GPT-3, GPT-4, BERT [15], and LLaMA [16], are a leading application of generative AI. Built on the transformer architecture [17], they are trained on massive datasets, enabling them to understand and generate human-like text [18]. In software engineering, LLMs like Codex translate natural language into code, suggest improvements,

and complete functions [2]. They are also used for summarizing code [19], bug detection, documentation, and in intelligent IDEs that provide real-time developer support [20], [21]. These tools speed up development, improve quality, and make coding more accessible.

2.3 ChatGPT

ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI, is based on the GPT architecture and is one of the most advanced LLM applications. Initially designed for conversation, it has become a powerful tool in software engineering. It can generate code from descriptions, assist in debugging by explaining errors, suggest optimizations, and even create documentation and comments for better code readability [22]. This makes ChatGPT a practical assistant across many stages of development.

3. RELATED WORK

In this section, we review related work that investigates the quality, correctness, and efficiency of code generated by Large Language Models (LLMs), particularly focusing on ChatGPT.

Several studies have evaluated the quality, correctness, and efficiency of code generated by ChatGPT and similar LLMs. Liu et al. [23] conducted one of the largest studies, analyzing 4,066 Java and Python snippets across 2,033 programming tasks. Their findings revealed frequent correctness and maintainability issues, along with suggested mitigation strategies. Similarly, Miah et al. [24] explored ChatGPT's use in R programming, noting its usefulness for simpler tasks but limitations with complex ones. They also reported average user performance of 1.61 attempts and 47.02 seconds per task, identifying conciseness as a weakness. Coello et al. [25] evaluated GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 on programming tasks using the MBPP dataset and provided quantitative insights into performance. Khan et al. [26] compared ChatGPT-generated code with human-written solutions across 131 prompts using 14 quality metrics, focusing on correctness, comprehensibility, and security. Liu et al. [27] introduced EvalPlus, a framework with additional test cases, showing a significant amount of previously undetected wrong code generated by LLMs. Liu et al. [28] assessed ChatGPT across 728 algorithm problems in five programming languages, examining correctness, complexity, and security. Buscemi [29] evaluated ChatGPT-3.5 in ten programming languages, reporting strong results in widely used languages like Python and Java but weaker performance in less common or syntactically

complex ones, suggesting a need for language-specific improvements.

While previous studies have examined LLM generated code across different languages and problem types, they rarely evaluate repeated generations of comparable tasks or focus specifically on C++ database management tasks. This study addresses that gap by analysing ChatGPT's behaviour across twenty structurally similar database management tasks, using measurable indicators such as generation time, code length, executability, and static analysis results. By applying a consistent task framework, this work offers a focused evaluation of ChatGPT's performance within this task domain and aligns the collected data with themes commonly reported in the literature including variability across generations, maintainability concerns, and differences in code structure and style.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study was designed to evaluate ChatGPT's ability to generate C++ code for twenty database management tasks that share the same functional requirements but differ in context. For each task, the model was prompted to produce one hundred independent programs, resulting in a consistent set of repeated generations. During each run, we recorded the generated code, measured the generation time, and documented code-length indicators such as the number of characters and lines of code. Each program was also assigned to one of several predefined structural categories to support later analysis. Finally, all generated programs were examined using Cppcheck to identify potential issues and compute task-level error density.

4.1 Selected Programming Language

In order to evaluate the code generation abilities of ChatGPT, a collection of 20 C++ database management tasks was chosen. C++ supports multiple programming paradigms, including procedural, object-oriented, and generic programming [30]. This flexibility makes it suitable for a wide range of applications, from simple programs to complex software systems. Additionally, C++ is widely adopted in fundamental programming courses at universities around the world [31], providing students with a strong foundation in core programming concepts such as memory management, data structures, and algorithm development. Its educational significance and strong presence in academic curricula make it an interesting and relevant choice for evaluating the code generation capabilities of large language models.

4.2 Model Configuration and Setup

In this study, ChatGPT GPT-4 was accessed through OpenAI's Python API [32]. Python version 3.11.2 was used to send requests to the model and handle the returned responses. During each interaction, three key parameters were defined to maintain uniformity across all experiments:

- 1) **Model version:** GPT-4o-2024-08-06, which includes notable enhancements such as structured output support, improved computational efficiency, and extended fine-tuning capabilities for domain-specific tasks.
- 2) **System role:** the model was assigned the system role, which determines the assistant's behavior and tone. The system message was set as "You are an intelligent assistant."
- 3) **User query:** the template used to request C++ code generation is described in Section 4.4, detailing the structure and consistency of prompts across all tasks.

4.3 Tasks

Twenty C++ database management tasks were developed for this study. These tasks were selected from exercises commonly used in undergraduate programming courses and coding challenge platforms. The tasks and the entities they manage are listed in Table 1. Each task required the implementation of the same core five functions: adding, deleting, updating, searching, and displaying records, but applied to different domains. This design ensures both consistency across tasks and variety in application, making them relevant and reflective of common programming practices.

Table 1: Selected C++ Database Management Tasks

Task Title	Entities Managed
Health Care Reservation System	Patients, Appointments
Self-service Supermarket System	Products, Locations
Car Cleaning System	Cars, Cleaners
Nursery Management System	Children, Babysitters
Sport Area Reservation System	Customers, Sport Areas
Coffee Shop Inventory System	Drinks, Suppliers
Tourism Guide System	Tourists, Attractions
Computer Parts Management System	Parts, Manufacturers
Student Registration System	Students, Courses
Library Management System	Students, Books
Hotel Reservation System	Guests, Rooms
Airline Booking System	Passengers, Flights
Inventory Management System	Items, Suppliers
Equipment Management System	Equipment, Labs
Book Publisher Management System	Books, Publishers
Beauty Salon Reservation System	Customers, Hairstylists

Car Insurance Service System	Cars, Insurance Companies
Furniture Inventory System	Furniture, Suppliers
Thirsty Station System	Customers, Shops
Electrical Grid System	Customers, Electricity Producers

4.4 Implementation

Algorithm 1 outlines the key steps in our experimental implementation for a single task. The algorithm takes as input the task title T , the programming language L and the list of required functions that manipulate the managed entities FE , as specified in the previous section. The algorithm begins by constructing the query Q , which is then input into ChatGPT. Thus, we have chosen the following simple query:

```
Implement a(n) {T} in {L}. The
system should be able to {FE}. Do
not import libraries or include
comments within the code.
```

Our selected query employs simple language and concise commands to guide the model toward a clear output structure. It explicitly prevents the use of external libraries to avoid reliance on pre-written code and built-in functionalities, and it excludes comments to keep the generated code clean and easy to read. The query was deliberately kept minimal, without prescribing detailed implementation steps. This gave ChatGPT the freedom to interpret each task independently, allowing us to observe how consistently it responds and whether its understanding is influenced by the task title.

After generating the query Q , we pass it to ChatGPT via the OpenAI API. When the output is successfully generated, we process it to distinguish the code C from other text.

Algorithm 1 implementation

```
1: Input: Task Title  $T$ , Programming
   Language  $L$ , Required Functions  $FE$ 
2: Initialize: iter=0
3: Definitions:  $Q$  means query input into
   ChatGPT api,  $I$  means maximum number
   of iterations,  $O$  means output returned by
   api call,  $C$  means generated  $L$  code
4:  $Q \leftarrow \text{generate\_query}(T, L, FE)$ 
5: while iter <  $I$  do
6:    $O \leftarrow \text{call\_api}(Q)$ 
7:   If successful( $O$ ) then
8:      $C \leftarrow \text{process}(O, L)$ 
9:     iter++
10:  end if
11: end while
```

5. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we assess the performance of ChatGPT GPT-4 in generating code to implement the tasks outlined in Table 1. The evaluation covers four dimensions: code-generation categories, time performance, code length, and static code quality.

5.1 Experimental Execution

For each of the twenty database management tasks described in Section 4.3, ChatGPT GPT-4 was requested to generate code 100 independent times, producing a total of 2,000 C++ code samples. Repeating the generation process multiple times ensured consistency in the analyses and improved the reliability of the collected data.

All tests were conducted on a MacBook Pro (macOS) equipped with a 2.5 GHz Quad-Core Intel Core i7 processor and 16 GB RAM. The generated C++ programs were compiled and executed using Xcode version 13.2.1, ensuring uniform testing conditions across all experiments.

5.2 Code Generation Categories and Distribution

To enable systematic analysis, all generated C++ programs were grouped according to the programming paradigm employed either procedural or object-oriented, as this distinction influences program organization and data handling. Each program was further classified into one of four categories based on its structure and testing requirements:

- 1) **Procedural – Human Input (P–HI):** Procedural programs that require user interaction. They typically employ a struct data type to manage records and include a menu-driven interface that repeatedly prompts the user for input until exit.
- 2) **Procedural – No Human Input (P–NoHI):** Procedural programs that execute automatically, invoking selected functions in main() to test system features without user input.
- 3) **Object-Oriented – Human Input (OO–HI):** Object-oriented programs that encapsulate data and methods within classes and rely on iterative menus for user input and testing.
- 4) **Object-Oriented – No Human Input (OO–NoHI):** Object-oriented programs that operate without manual interaction, generating predefined objects and testing a subset of the system's functionality.

Figure 1 presents the distribution of these categories across all generated C++ database

management tasks. The degree of user interaction varied: some programs required manual menu inputs, whereas others executed automatically with predefined data. Automatic versions typically focused on limited functions within each system, with the tested components differing slightly between runs.

Across tasks, the Object-Oriented – No Human Input (OO–NoHI) category appeared most frequently, while the Procedural – No Human Input (P–NoHI) type was least common. The Object-Oriented – Human Input (OO–HI) and Procedural – Human Input (P–HI) categories occurred with moderate frequency, reflecting variability in how ChatGPT interprets task descriptions and testing requirements. This variation highlights both the structural diversity and the inherent unpredictability of the model’s outputs, providing a foundation for the subsequent analyses of generation time, code length, and static code quality. The full dataset of generated outputs is available on GitHub [33].

Figure 1: Code distribution of ChatGPT-generated C++ outputs across four categories.

5.3 Time Performance Analysis

To examine generation efficiency, the time taken by ChatGPT to produce code for each of the twenty database management tasks was recorded over one hundred independent runs. For every task, three key measures were collected: the minimum, maximum, and mean generation times (in seconds). These values reflect both the fastest and slowest generation cases, as well as the average response duration, offering insight into how generation speed fluctuates across repeated trials.

Figure 2 presents the distribution of generation times (minimum–maximum) alongside the mean for

each task. The results show noticeable variation among tasks, reflecting differences in code complexity, prompt interpretation, and internal randomness during generation. The Self-Service Supermarket System achieved the shortest minimum time (approximately 5.7 seconds), while the Student Registration System recorded the longest maximum time (around 114 seconds).

Figure 2: Generation time per task (Min–Max range with Mean).

To assess the consistency of performance, the Coefficient of Variation (CV) was computed for each task using:

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \times 100$$

where σ denotes the standard deviation and μ the mean generation time. A lower CV indicates more stable generation speed across runs. Figure 3 shows the mean generation time and its corresponding CV for each task.

Overall, the mean generation time across tasks ranged from approximately 13 to 28 seconds, suggesting that ChatGPT maintained moderate response times for most medium-sized programming tasks. However, the variation between runs indicates that generation speed is not fully consistent. Tasks such as the Student Registration System and Nursery Management System showed the highest CV values, revealing noticeable differences in generation time. In contrast, the Inventory Management System and Thirsty Station System showed lower CV values, indicating relatively steadier performance. These results highlight that while ChatGPT can produce code efficiently, its generation time remains subject to randomness inherent in large language model inference.

Figure 3: Mean code-generation time and variability (CV) across database management tasks.

5.4 Code Length Analysis

To assess the structural complexity and consistency of the generated programs, two metrics were examined: Number of Characters (NOC) and Lines of Code (LOC). These measures reflect both the textual volume and the logical structure of each C++ program, offering insight into how concisely or extensively ChatGPT expresses similar functionality across different tasks.

For every task, the minimum, maximum, and mean values of NOC and LOC were calculated across 100 independent generations. Figure 4 and Figure 5 illustrate the variation in code length, showing both the range (minimum to maximum) and mean values for each metric. The results reveal noticeable differences among tasks. Systems such as the Health Care Reservation System and Tourism Guide System produced relatively long programs, averaging around 3,900 characters and 130 lines, while tasks such as the Self-Service Supermarket System and Computer Parts Management System produced short programs, averaging about 2,700 characters and 100 lines.

To further assess the consistency of code generation, the Coefficient of Variation (CV) was computed for each metric using:

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \times 100$$

where σ denotes the standard deviation and μ the mean value across all runs. A lower CV indicates greater consistency in code size between repeated generations of the same task.

As shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, the Library Management System and Thirsty Station System recorded the lowest CV values (about 8–13%), indicating relatively stable program size across runs.

In contrast, the Self-Service Supermarket System and Computer Parts Management System showed the highest CV values (about 19–24%), reflecting greater variation between generations. Overall, the code length analysis reveals variability across tasks, indicating that the model’s interpretation and structuring of domains are not always consistent.

Figure 4: Code length per task measured by number of characters.

Figure 5: Code length per task measured by lines of code.

5.5 Code Static Analysis

To evaluate the structural quality and maintainability of the generated C++ programs, all source files were analyzed using Cppcheck, a static-analysis tool that inspects code without execution [34]. This stage followed the evaluation of generation time and code length, providing a deeper assessment of syntactic correctness and adherence to coding standards. Cppcheck classifies findings into six severity levels, Error, Warning, Style,

Performance, Portability, and Information, each representing a different dimension of software quality. Table 2 summarizes these severity levels and their corresponding descriptions [7]. In this study, the analysis focuses on the first three severities, Error, Warning, and Style, which most directly influence correctness, reliability, and maintainability.

Table 2: Severity Levels Generated by Cppcheck

Severity Level	Description
error	when code is executed there is either undefined behavior or other error, such as a memory leak or resource leak
warning	when code is executed there might be undefined behavior
style	stylistic issues, such as unused functions, redundant code, constness, operator precedence, possible mistakes.
performance	run time performance suggestions based on common knowledge, though it is not certain any measurable speed difference will be achieved by fixing these messages.
portability	portability warnings. Implementation defined behavior. 64-bit portability. Some undefined behavior that probably works "as you want", etc.
information	configuration problems, which does not relate to the syntactical correctness, but the used Cppcheck configuration could be improved.

1) Error Density Calculation

To enable comparison across programs of different lengths, the Error Density (ED) metric was used to measure the number of detected issues per thousand lines of code (KLOC). For each generated version, the following formula was applied:

$$ED_i = \frac{\text{Error} + \text{Warning} + \text{Style}}{\text{Line of Code}} \times 1000$$

Each task's overall value was then aggregated across all 100 runs to obtain the task-level weighted error density (ED_t):

$$ED_t = \frac{\sum(\text{Error} + \text{Warning} + \text{Style})}{\sum \text{Lines of Code}} \times 1000$$

This weighted approach accounts for variation in program size and ensures that all generated runs contribute proportionally to the final metric. The error-density concept is widely used in software-engineering research to assess code quality and maintainability [35].

2) Results and Observations

Figure 6 presents the aggregated static-analysis results across all twenty tasks. The computed task-

level ED_t values range from 47 to 71 issues per KLOC, with an overall mean of roughly 58 issues per KLOC. These relatively low values indicate that the generated code is well-structured and free of major correctness problems. The Self-Service Supermarket System recorded the highest ED_t (≈ 71), mainly due to stylistic and duplicate-definition findings. Conversely, the Health Care Reservation System achieved the lowest ED_t (≈ 47) even though it produced the longest programs, highlighting that code length does not necessarily imply lower structural quality or defect frequency.

Figure 6: Aggregated Cppcheck results showing task-level error density (ED_t) across all generated C++ programs.

3) Nature of the Detected Issues

Most of the detected issues were stylistic suggestions rather than functional errors. Common examples included recommendations such as passing non-modified parameters by constant reference (`constParameterReference`), declaring loop variables as constant (`constVariableReference`), and using standard STL algorithms instead of manual loops (`useStlAlgorithm`). These findings improve readability and maintainability but have no effect on program correctness. Warnings appeared infrequently and were mainly related to uninitialized variables (`uninitMemberVar`) or redundant pointer checks (`nullPointerRedundantCheck`), some of which were false positives. True errors were rare and primarily involved duplicate-definition notices (`ctuOneDefinitionRuleViolation`) resulting from identical class names saved in multiple files. A single instance of `virtualDestructor` was also detected, which could be resolved easily by declaring a virtual destructor in the base class.

5.6 Cross-Metric Observation

To further understand how performance and structural factors relate to code quality, an extended cross-metric analysis was performed. Two relationships were examined using task-level aggregates:

1. Generation Time vs Error Density (ED_t): represents efficiency relative to static quality.
2. Code Length vs Error Density (ED_t): represents complexity relative to static quality.

As shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8, neither relationship displayed a strong trend. Tasks with longer generation times or larger program size did not consistently show higher error densities. These results indicate that ChatGPT maintains consistent code quality across varying generation sizes and durations. In these figures, abbreviated task names are used to improve clarity and conserve space within the plots.

Figure 7: Error density (ED_t) versus mean generation time for all tasks.

5.7 ChatGPT Limitations

Although ChatGPT successfully generated functional and executable C++ programs across all tasks, several limitations were observed during the experiments.

1. The model showed noticeable variability in code structure and length across repeated runs of the same task. This variation, reflected in the higher coefficients of variation (CV) reported in Figure 4 and Figure 5, indicates that the model does not always produce consistent implementations even under identical conditions.

2. While most detected issues were stylistic rather than functional, the static analysis results (Figure 6) revealed that some tasks showed higher error-density values (ED_t), suggesting variations in code quality.
3. The execution time was not uniform across tasks as some required longer generation periods reflecting differences in model reasoning complexity.
4. Tasks generated without human input occasionally missed some system functions or provided limited internal testing, reducing the completeness of those implementations.

Figure 8: Error density (ED_t) versus mean generation time for all tasks.

6. COMPARISON WITH EXISTING WORKS

The findings of this study show several points of alignment with recent evaluations of LLM-generated code. Liu et al. [23] reported that ChatGPT-generated programs often require refinement for maintainability, which is consistent with our Cppcheck results where most issues were stylistic rather than functional. Miah and Zhu [24] identified conciseness as a relative weakness in ChatGPT’s R code generation, and a similar pattern appeared in our work through the variation in code length across 2,000 C++ outputs. Coello et al. [25] noted non-deterministic behavior in ChatGPT’s outputs, with the model sometimes producing different implementations of the same task. This behaviour was also evident in our repeated generations, where structural differences were common across runs. Khan et al. [26] observed clear stylistic and structural differences between ChatGPT-generated and human-written code, which aligns with our finding that the generated programs were consistently

compilable but varied noticeably in formatting and structure. Buscemi [29] also reported variability and inconsistency across tasks and languages. Although our study focuses only on C++, the variability we observed across the twenty tasks reflects similar tendencies.

Liu et al. [27] showed that programs that appear correct may still fail more comprehensive test cases, highlighting the value of deeper behavioural evaluation. Our study did not include input-based functional testing, especially for tasks without user interaction, so such issues were outside the scope of this work. Liu et al. [28] further demonstrated that ChatGPT's code quality can vary across problem types and may include non-functional issues. We observed comparable variation in code size, structure, and maintainability indicators.

Overall, the behaviour seen in our database-management tasks aligns with broader trends reported in the literature, particularly in terms of maintainability, variability, and stylistic inconsistency. These patterns suggest that while ChatGPT can reliably generate workable C++ programs, its output remains sensitive to prompt repetition and task formulation. Future work could extend this evaluation by incorporating functional correctness and security testing.

7. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated ChatGPT's ability to generate executable C++ programs across twenty database management tasks. Our objectives were to assess the correctness of the generated code, examine its structural characteristics, measure variability across repeated generations, and analyse static quality using Cppcheck. The results show that ChatGPT was able to consistently produce compilable and runnable C++ programs for all tasks, indicating reliable performance within this domain. Across 2,000 generated programs, we observed clear variation in code length, structure, and category, reflecting the model's non-deterministic behaviour. The static analysis results revealed no critical errors, with most findings related to style or maintainability. Together, these observations indicate that ChatGPT can produce functional C++ solutions while showing variability typical of large language models.

Limitations. This study has several limitations. The evaluation focused on a single programming language (C++) and one LLM model (GPT-4o), which limits the generalisability of the findings. The analysis considered compilation outcomes, structural

patterns, and static quality, but did not assess functional correctness using real or simulated inputs, particularly for tasks that do not require user interaction. The tasks were limited to database-management scenarios, so results may differ for more complex or algorithmic problems. The study also did not include security analysis or detailed runtime performance profiling. These limitations indicate opportunities for expanding the evaluation in future research.

Future Work. Future research will assess the functional correctness of the generated programs by testing their behaviour with input data. The dataset from this study, which includes metrics such as code size, generation time, and static-analysis results, may be used to develop machine learning models that predict or classify the quality of LLM-generated code. Further studies may also compare different programming languages and model versions to better understand how model architecture and task characteristics influence code-generation behaviour.

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